

DESCRIPTION OF RELIEF ON TOPOGRAPHIC MAPS USING GAT
PROGRAMS

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Abstract. The plan, the description of the relief on the cards largely determines the description of all other elements of the content of the card and plans. Without describing the relief with sufficient accuracy and studying it in detail on plans and maps, it is impossible to study the connection between individual elements of the landscape, as well as to use natural resources effectively. This article describes the convenience of creating terrain on topographic maps based on GAT.

Keywords: Plan, map, GAT, Google Earth, ArcToolbox, Special Analysis, .pgx, relief, horizontals.

Enter. Horizontals allow for a mathematically accurate representation of the plan view of individual forms and elements of the relief. Through them, it is possible to determine the slope, the angle of the slope and the direction of the falls. These problems are solved on the basis of sets of properties related to the method of describing the terrain using horizontal lines. On topographic maps and plans, the relief is shown using horizontal lines. Horizontal-height refers to the curves connecting the same points. The horizontals are separated from each other by a given vertical distance from the accepted surface, known as the elevation of the relief section.

The elevations and depressions of the earth's surface are called relief. The topography of the place is divided into highs and lows. When describing the terrain

on topographic maps and plans, the conditions for quickly finding the heights of the points, determining the slope directions and steepness, and getting a good understanding of the depicted terrain and the mutual location of some of its forms are set. To describe the relief, specific points on the earth's surface and the elevations of points along the lines are found, which would be difficult to read if all of them were displayed on a map. Therefore, in order to satisfy the conditions listed above, the method of horizontal lines is used in the description of the relief, along with writing some of the bland points

Picture 1. The main forms of relief

Creating relief on topographic maps in GAT software is the most complex and responsible task. To do this, we first determine the geographic location of the area and determine the location from the Google Earth program. We can create otmetka points throughout the region by the command "Sozdat put". (picture 3.)

**Picture 2. Obtaining map data from Google Earth
Then we can save the resulting line in .kml format. (Picture 3)**

**Picture 3. Saving data from Google Earth program
Picture 4. Google Earth program
Data conversion from Google Earth**

Then we can convert the resulting .kml file to open it in the ArcMap application through the link <https://www.gpsvisualizer.com/>. (Picture 4)

We can open the generated file in .gpx format using the "from gpx" command of the Conversion section in the ArcToolbox command panel of the ArcMap application (Fig. 5, 6)

Figure 5. Adding the converted data to the ArcMap application **6. A view of the data added to the ArcMap application**

Then we create a height model of the place using the height values of the points in the interpolation method from the Special Analysis command section. (Figure 7)

Figure 7. The height model of the place created on the basis of the obtained data is Fig. **8. Creating horizontals based on the created height model**

Then, from the Special Analysis command section, we combine points with the same height to form horizontal lines (Picture 8).

As a result, we have a digital topographic map relief of the researched area.

Summary. In cartography, special attention is paid to the cartographic method of research, that is, to the use of structured maps in practical work. Today, scientific-informational mapping is entering various economic spheres - population, industry, agriculture, etc. In order to perform these tasks, it is very important that all information is open, that GAT and mathematical methods, automated tools are involved in the mapping work. There is a need to carry out mapping in regional development at the national level and at the regional level. At the regional level, things can develop rapidly, because the economic indicators of each regional division are changing rapidly, and specific economic relations are being established between the regions.

List of used literature

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